

THE CHINA FACTOR IN INDIA-JAPAN RELATIONS: AN INTERPRETATION

Prasanta Sahoo

Head, Department of Political Science, Kendrapara Autonomous College, Kendrapara, Odisha -754211

Prof. Anil Kumar Mohapatra

Professor of Political Science, Dept. of Social Science, Fakir Mohan University, Balasore, Odisha -756089

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Abstract

This research paper delves into the multifaceted dimensions of the bilateral cooperation between the two oldest democracies of Asia India and Japan in the 21st Century, examining the political, economic, defence & security and cultural aspects. The formal diplomatic relations between the two nations have been established in April 1952. Both nations have close economic relations since 1991. They have strong defence & security cooperation since 2008. In the recent years, the defense exchanges between the two nations have gained strength due to the issues of peace, security and stability in the “Indo-Pacific region”. They have also centuries-old cultural & civilizational ties enriched by the shared heritage of the Buddhism dating back to 4th Century A.D. Moreover, the study finds that both India and Japan have come closer for making a balance of power in the Asian continent against the backdrop of the aggressive China in South Asia and South China Sea.

Keywords: *India-Japan relations, Buddhism, Indo-Pacific Region, China Factor, QUAD*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the wake of rapidly changing geopolitical scenarios in Asia, India-Japan relations have great political, economic and strategic convergence. Today India and Japan share a “Special Strategic & Global Partnership”. It is one of the most dynamic bilateral partnerships between the two nations in the 21st Century. Both nations are two natural partners of the Asia-Pacific region. They are two key players committed for establishing security, peace and prosperity in the Indo-Pacific region. They share the common values of democracy, freedom, rule of law and respect for fundamental rights. Indo-Japan relations are mutually beneficially as well as

complementary (Singh, 2022). Both India & Japan are functioning and vibrant democracies. Both are aspirants for permanent membership in the United Nations Security Council (UNSC). Both stand together with a cooperative and comprehensive approach to combat the international terrorism as well as sea-piracy. In fact, over the years mutual trust has been strengthened with Japanese emergency support following the security dialogue on the 2+2 format; Malabar exercises; cost guards exercises; Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement etc. (Basu, 2014). However, now both nations are facing several problems namely; national security, maritime security, regional economic disparity etc. In fact, these problems are emerging from the coercive and threatening behaviour of China in South Asia and South China Sea, thus intensifying close ties between the two Asian democracies India and Japan (Alam, 2019). For instance, in the recent years, China has intervened in the region of influence of India in South Asia through different activities and projects like; the One Belt One Road initiative (OBOR) of China and the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (passing through the Indian Union Territory of Jammu & Kashmir). China has also encircled and encroached upon the sphere of influence of India in the Indian Ocean by establishing its ports in Gwadar of Pakistan and Hambantota of Sri Lanka (Kumar, 2020). Additionally, on account of the unresolved border disputes both India and China have confronted many deadly military clashes ever since the Sino-India War of 1962. The recent military stand-offs along their contested boundary i.e. the Line of Actual Control (LAC) include the Galwan River Valley Clash in June 2020, the Pangong Sector Skirmishes in August and September 2020 and the Tawang Sector Clash in December 2022. In the recent years, following such deadly military clashes with China, India has developed more close and strong relations with its Quad partners like; the US, Japan, and Australia (Sahoo, 2024). However, most recently in October 2024 both India and China have reached an agreement on patrolling arrangements along the 'Line of Actual Control' (LAC) in the border areas leading to disengagement of troops at two friction points namely; Depsang and Demchok in the eastern Ladakh and a resolution of the issues that had arisen four years back in the Galwan River Valley Clash in 2020. Similarly, the approach of China towards the South China Sea has disturbed Japan too. It is evident from the pages of the recorded history that in 663AD there took place the Battle of Baekgang (first conflict) between China and Japan. Additionally, between 1880 and 1945 there were a series of wars and confrontations between the two nations. In the recent years, due to the coercive behaviour of China, Japan has increased its defense budget and also set up new military bases in order to

tackle the national security threats. In such a background, it is here essential to understand the history and the evolution of the bilateral ties between the two key Asian nations.

2.HISTORICAL CIRCUMSTANCES

The origins of India-Japan relations lie in the spiritual affinity and strong cultural and civilizational ties between the two nations. The cultural connections between the two nations can be traced back to the 4th Century A.D when Buddhism, born in India, reached to Japan via China and Korea and spread throughout the islands, thus establishing a permanent connection between the two nations. In Japan, Buddhism has become a major religion. It has brought the worship of many Hindu gods. The Shichifukujin or the seven lucky gods of Japan have their origins in Hindu traditions. The earliest documented direct contact of India with Japan was the ‘Todaiji Temple’ in Nara, where the consecration of the towering statute of the Lord Buddha was performed by an Indian monk Bodhisena in 752A.D. The Prince Shotoku Taishi (574 - 622) was one of the most influential figures in the political, cultural and ethical spheres of Japan. Prince Shotoku Taishi is regarded as the founder of Japanese nation and Buddhism in Japan. In fact, it was Prince Taishi who blended Confucianism and Buddhism into the mainstream of the political, social and ethical codes of Japan. In the early modern age, many prominent Indians who visited to Japan were like; Swami Vivekananda, Nobel laureate Rabindranath Tagore, entrepreneur JRD Tata, freedom fighter Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose, Rash Behari Bose and Justice Radha Binod Pal. Among these great Indian figures, Swami Vivekananda first visited Japan. In year 1893, Swamiji made his journey through Japan to the World Religious Parliament, Chicago, US. The Nobel laureate Tagore had five-time visits to Japan (thrice in 1916, 1917 & 1924 and twice in 1929). In fact, Tagore’s visits revived the age-old connections between the cultures of two nations (Singh, 2022). Because of these close contacts between Rabindranath Tagore and Japan, Visva Bharati University set up a Japanese Department in 1954 (Sahu, 2024). Thus, it is found that there is vast and profound influence of Indian culture (Buddhism) upon Japan. From the ancient times to the current times, Buddhism has played a great role in unifying the two key Asian countries India and Japan.

2.1. INDIA-JAPAN RELATIONS FROM 1945 to 2000

After the World War II came to end in 1945, the entire world was ideologically bifurcated into the two power blocs namely; the Western Bloc led by the United States of America (USA) and the Eastern Bloc led by the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), leading to the beginning of the Cold War. Japan was in ruins due to its defeat in the World War II and had to rebuild, while India was impoverished and diminished by the British rule. Both nations

confronted may similar socio-economic challenges. During the freedom struggle of India against the British colonialism, Japan helped the Indian National Army of Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose. After India's independence in August 1947, the first Prime Minister Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru had gifted two elephants to Tokyo's Ueno Zoo in 1949. In fact, it was a symbolic gift of India for Japan's good fortune and brought a glimmer of hope into the lives of the people of Japan. Japan was invited to New Delhi for the first Asian Games in 1951. Next year in April 1952, India and Japan concluded a peace treaty and established their diplomatic relations. India supported Japan to be a member of the United Nations (UN) in 1952. In 1955, the leaders of both nations met at the Badung Afro-Asian Conference (Indonesia) (Singh, 2022). During the rebuilding of its economy after the devastation in the Second World War Japan was assisted greatly by India with the supply of the essential minerals, mainly iron ore. In 1957, Japan's Prime Minister Nobusuke Kishi visited to India. Following his visit, Japan started providing yen loans to India in 1958. However, this relationship did not have much impacts as Japan was caught in the rivalry of the two power blocs (the USA & the USSR) and was forced to align itself with the West power bloc, while India followed non-alignment as its best policy in order to maintain equal-distance from the two power blocs. Additionally, Japan also maintained neutrality when India had wars with China and Pakistan. Here it was found that the bilateral relationship between India and Japan was of low intensity until the end of the Cold War in 1991.

After the collapse of the USSR in 1991, India adopted the Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization model (New Economic Policy) that provided a vast market for the Japanese products and the old relationship of trust between the two nations revived. In the same year, India introduced its 'Look East Policy' (now called the 'Act East Policy' since 2014) to improve relations with the ASEAN and other East Asian countries. However, the nuclear tests in Pokhran in 1998 by India disturbed the bilateral relationship between the two nations again. Following the testing of the nuclear devices in 1998, Japan imposed sanctions against India as a punitive arrangement. The Japanese Diet found these tests as a threat to the very existence of humanity. Japan froze grants-in-aid for new projects, suspended Yen loans, disallowed Tokyo as a venue for India Development Forum and put stringent regulations on technology transfer. Japan suspended the Official Development Assistance (ODA) to India. India was the biggest receiver of the Japanese ODA from 1986 to 1998 except in 1990. Hence, for about three years from 1998 to 2000, due to the issue of the nuclear tests, both nations had unfriendly relations. However, the hostile relationship between the two nations got resolved in the hands

of the Japanese Prime Minister Mr. Yoshiro Mori and the Indian Prime Minister Mr. Atal Bihari Vajpayee.

2.2. A NEW TRAJECTORY SINCE 2000

The 21st Century witnessed a very warm and cordial cooperation between the two civilizational partners India and Japan. From 2000 onwards Indo-Japan bilateral relationship improved significantly. In fact, following the historic visit of the Prime Minister of Japan Mr. Yoshiro Mori to India in August 2000, the diplomatic and economic sanctions imposed by Japan against India were lifted and their bilateral relationship came back to normal condition. During this visit the Japanese Prime Minister Mr. Yoshiro Mori and his Indian counterpart Shri Atal Bihari Vajpayee established the “Global Partnership” between the two nations, thus gaining a new trajectory in the bilateral relationship in the 21st Century. In 2006, Indian PM Dr. Manmohan Singh visited to Japan. His visit to Japan was very much important because he and his Japanese counterpart Mr. Shinzo Abe upgraded the bilateral relationship from a “Global Partnership” to a “Strategic and Global Partnership”. In addition, after becoming the Prime Minister of India Shri Narendra Modi visited to Japan in September 2014. During this visit the PM Modi and his Japanese counterpart Abe further elevated the bilateral relationship to a “Special Strategic and Global Partnership”.

3. THE CHINA FACTOR

In the recent past, it has been found that the Centre of gravity of the global politics has shifted from the Atlantic to the Pacific due to several structural factors like; the rise of both nations China and India, Japan’s assertion of military profile and a major shift in the US global force posture in favour of the Asia Pacific, which is manifest in its policy US Pivot and Rebalancing towards Asia (Sahu, 2024). The rise of China in Asia has disturbed the equilibrium and created a sense of fear among other states in the region. The economic and military capabilities of China, along with its coercive and threatening behaviour in South Asia and the South China have become worries for both India and Japan. According to the theory of realism, two countries should come together to balance the rise of China and failing to do so would be risky for both (Kumar, 2020).

Today, the China’s foreign policy is oriented towards augmenting its economic and military prowess in order to achieve the regional hegemony in Asia. As a result, both nations India and Japan have the common threats from the coercive behaviour of China in the Asia-Pacific region and they see China as their common enemy. Additionally, China has always opposed to the restructuring of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) to include India and Japan as

permanent members (Sahu, 2024). In such a background, following the ‘Theory of Realism’ two nations have come closer to deter China in the region. For example, the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (QUAD) is one of such initiatives taken by the four democracies: the United States, India, Japan and Australia (Mohapatra,2024). Moreover, ever since its establishment in 2007 and revitalization in 2017, the Quad has emerged as an important platform to promote peace, stability, cooperation and prosperity in the Indo-Pacific region, most importantly countering the growing influence and coercive behaviour of China in the Asia-Pacific and Indo-Pacific regions and ensuring a free, open, and inclusive regional order. The recent Quad Leaders’ Summit hosted by the US President Joe Biden, at Wilmington, Delaware on September 21, 2024 found all the Quad countries more strategically aligned than ever before in the 21st Century. In this summit, the Prime Minister of India Shri Narendra Modi stated that a free, open, inclusive and prosperous Indo-Pacific is a shared objective of all the Quad partners, underlining that the Quad is here to stay, to assist, to partner and to complement the efforts of the “Indo-Pacific nations”. It can be said here that under the umbrella of the Quad, four democracies have come closer to deter the aggressive behaviour of China in Indo-Pacific region. India’s Act East Policy, that envisions active engagements with the Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the East Asia remains largely anchored upon the Japanese support. Japan facilitated India’s participation in the East Asia Summit and the East Asia Community proposed by Japan to deter China’s proposal of an East Asian Free Trade included India too. While China opposed to include India, Australia and New Zealand in the Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN), Japan strongly supported their inclusion in it (Sahu, 2024). Thus, from the above discussion it is evident that that China’s rise in the Asia-Pacific region is the most important factor that has pushed both nations India and Japan to be more united in the recent years.

4.KEY BILATERAL VISITS

It will discuss the high-level political visits of the Prime Ministers of both countries India and Japan. Since the establishment of their formal diplomatic relations, both nations have had several exchanges of visits by the Prime Ministers. From 1957 to 2023, it has been found that a number of Indian Prime Ministers have visited Japan. They are Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, Indira Gandhi, Rajib Gandhi, P.V. Narasimha Rao, Atal Bihari Vajpayee, Dr. Manmohan Singh and Narendra Modi. During the same period a number of Japanese counterparts have also paid their visits to India. They are like Hayato Ikeda, Yasuhiro Nakasone, Toshiaki Kaifu, Yoshiro Mori, Junichiro Koizumi, Yukio Hotoyama , Yoshihiko Noda , Shinzo Abe and Fumio

Kishida. In the recent years, the frequency of visits by the Prime Ministers of both countries has increased. In March 2023, the Japanese Prime Minister Mr. Fumio Kishida visited India and in May of the same year the Indian Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi visited Japan and held a bilateral meeting with the Japanese Prime Minister Mr. Fumio Kishida on the margins of the G-7 Summit held in Hiroshima. In September 2023, Prime Minister Mr. Fumio Kishida had his second visit to India on the sidelines of the G20 Summit held at Bharat Mandapam, Delhi. From 2014 to 2023, the Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi visited Japan for six times. In fact, these visits of the leaders from both sides indicate that both India and Japan give importance to each other, thus strengthening the bilateral ties in a high degree of congruence of political, economic and strategic interests.

5. FORMS OF ENGAGEMENT

Over the years, the partnership between India and Japan has evolved into a multifaceted alliance characterized by the political, economic, defense & security and cultural engagements. They are discussed below.

(a) Political Relations:

India and Japan have regular as well as cordial political relations. The political and diplomatic relationship between the two countries have started with the conclusion of their 'Peace Treaty' in April 1952. There have been regular India-Japan annual summit meetings in each other's capitals since 2006. Because of the cordial political relations and the regular high level political engagements of the political leaders between the two nations, their bilateral relationship has been elevated to a "Special Strategic and Global Partnership" since 2014. In 2015, the Japanese Prime Minister Mr. Shinzo Abe visited to India and held bilateral meeting with the Indian Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi. In this meeting two leaders resolved to transform the India-Japan "Special Strategic and Global Partnership" into a deep, broad-based and action-oriented partnership, thus reflecting a broad convergence of their long-term political, economic and strategic goals. Both leaders also announced "Japan-India Vision 2025" to work together for the peace and prosperity of the Indo-Pacific region and the World. In May 2023, the PM Modi paid a visit to Japan to attend the G7 Summit in Hiroshima and held bilateral meeting with the PM Kishida. In September 2023, the PM Kishida visited to India to attend the G20 Summit and held bilateral meeting with the PM Modi. During this bilateral meeting, both leaders discussed their priorities for their G7 & G20 Presidencies, mainly in bringing the aspirations of the Global South to the fore. In addition, the PM Narendra Modi's most recent bilateral meeting with newly appointed Japan's Prime Minister Shigeru Ishiba on the margins of the 21st

ASEAN-India Summit and the 19th East Asia Summit held at Vientiane, Laos from 10th-11th October 2024 has further deepened the bilateral ties between the two nations in different sectors, encompassing the infrastructure, connectivity and defense. During this bilateral meeting both leaders have reaffirmed their commitments to a peaceful, safe and prosperous “Indo-Pacific region”, recognizing India & Japan as the indispensable natural partners of the Asian continent.

(b) Economic Ties:

India and Japan have strong economic cooperation in multiple sectors. They have vibrant economic engagements over the years. The bilateral trade relations strengthened in 1991, when India adopted the Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization or LPG model (New Economic Policy), under the Prime Ministership of Mr. P.V. Narasimha Rao, thus providing a vast market for the Japanese products. The economic relations between the two nations have significantly expanded and deepened over the years, particularly after the signing of the India-Japan CEPA (Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement) in 2011. As of November 2024, among the five largest economies of the world, Japan and India rank the 4th & 5th positions respectively after the US, China and Germany. As of early 2024, India-Japan bilateral trade was valued at approximately USD 20 billion. In fact, the economies of the two nations are complementary to each other. Japan is a developed economy, while India is a developing one. India has a big market with enormous amount of business and investment opportunities for Japanese investors and businessmen.

Japan-India Trade (Yen: Billion)

Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Trade from India to Japan	589	509	619	585	593	500	744	833	805
Trade from Japan to India	981	889	1,044	1,236	1,176	1,021	1,423	2,018	2,333

Source: Japanese Government Documents

Notably, India’s major exports to Japan include engineering goods, petroleum products, chemicals, agricultural products gems etc., while major Japanese exports to India include machinery, automobiles, electronics, steel products etc. Many Japanese automobile industries like Yamaha, Toyota, Nissan, Honda and Maruti Suzuki are active in India. Similarly in the

electronic sectors too, there are several Japanese firms like Sony, Panasonic, Canon, and Sharp that have invested huge money and have manufacturing units in Indian market.

In the recent years, Japanese Foreign Direct Investment in India has increased. But it remains small compared to the total outward FDI of Japan. Japanese outward FDI to India in FY 2021-22, FY 2022-23, and FY 2023-24 stood at USD 1.49 billion, 1.79 billion and 3.17 billion respectively. Cumulatively, from April 2000 to March 2024, the investments to India have been around USD 42.55 billion ranking Japan the fifth among source countries for FDI and accounting for 6.1 % of total FDI into India. Moreover, Japanese FDI into India has been primarily in automobiles, electrical equipment, general machinery, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, financial and insurance, construction, transportation, wholesale and retail and services sectors.

Direct Investment from Japan (Yen: Billion)

Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Direct Investment from Japan	368	564	357	371	522	214	493	641	1,082

Source: Japanese Government Documents

In fact, Japan sees India as a key partner in its “Free and Open Indo-Pacific” strategy and many government initiatives like “Make in India” and “Atmanirbhar Bharat” align with business interests of Japan. India has been the largest recipient of the Japanese Official Development Assistance over the past decades. Delhi Metro is the most successful example of the Japanese cooperation through the utilization of the Official Development Assistance (ODA). Japan continues to extend support in the strategic connectivity linking South Asia through the synergy between the “Act East Policy” and Partnership for Quality Infrastructure”. Moreover, the high-speed train is a key development in India for which Japan has extended financial support. Japan has also played a significant role in other sectors of India’s development like the environment, power and transportation (Alam, 2019).

(c) Defence Cooperation:

India-Japan defense relationship is the principal component of India-Japan “Special Strategic & Global Partnership”. Two nations have strong defense and security partnership. In the recent years, both nations have strengthened their defense cooperation, driven by the shared concerns over the regional peace, security and stability, mainly with regard to the growing influence of

China in the Indo-Pacific region. India and Japan hold regular joint military exercises in order to improve interoperability and foster closer defense relations. For example, they have conducted their first land based joint military exercise, that combined India's "Dharma Guardian" Exercise with the Ground Self -Defense Exercise of Japan. Both nations have signed several MoUs or agreements for defense cooperation such as the "Joint Declaration on Security Cooperation" in 2008, "Memorandum of Defense Cooperation and Exchanges" in 2014, the "General Security of Military Information Agreement in 2015, the "Implementation Arrangement for Deeper Cooperation in 2018 , the "Cyber Security Agreement" in 2019 and the "Acquisition and Cross-Servicing Agreement in 2020 .There are also key initiatives of security and defense dialogue between the two nations such as the Foreign and Defense Ministerial Meeting (2 + 2 Dialogue), annual Defense Ministerial Dialogue , Maritime Dialogue and Coast Guard-to-Coast Guard Dialogue. Japan has also shown its interests in exporting more advanced defense technologies to India, including missile defense systems and radar technologies. In addition, several defense companies of Japan are increasingly exploring opportunities with the defense manufactures of India under the "Make in India" initiative. Above all, India-Japan defense cooperation is evolving rapidly because both countries recognize the importance of their mutual security in an increasingly uncertain world.

(d) Cultural Relations:

Both nations have centuries-old cultural and civilizational bonds that date back to the 4th Century A.D, when Buddhism spread from India to Japan. Buddhism has a great influence upon the Japanese culture. Trade along the Silk Routes facilitated early cultural exchanges between the two countries. The Japan-India Association was established in 1903 and is the oldest international friendship body of Japan. Coming to the modern times, they have signed the "Cultural Agreement" in 1957, thus establishing cultural exchange programs. Today, the growing importance of the 'Yoga' and the 'Ayurveda' and much interest in Bollywood films in Japan and gaining readership of Japanese literature and influence of Japanese movies in India have enhanced the cultural relationship between the two nations. The recent cultural ties between the two nations have flourished, reflecting strong mutual interests in strengthening ties across various domains that encompass arts, heritage, education, and tourism. In 2022-23, both nations have organized a series of cultural exchanges, festivals and exhibitions for commemorating the 70th anniversary of their diplomatic relationship. Events such as the Indian Festival in Japan and Japanese Festival in India have also provided platforms in order to showcase the traditional art forms, performances, cuisine and films from both nations.

Moreover, both nations continue to collaborate through the Japan-India Cultural Centre in New Delhi, hosting a wide range of cultural performances, film screening and educational seminars on traditional Japanese culture and modern Japanese arts. Above all, India and Japan give importance to each other's traditions and have invested in promoting cultural understanding as a part of their broader diplomatic goals.

6. CONCLUSION

In view of the aforesaid facts, it can be concluded that India and Japan relations have a long history dating back to the ancient times. Bilateral relations however were at low level until 1990s. But from 2000 onwards the bilateral relations improved significantly and today, two nations share a "Special Strategic and Global Partnership". Both nations are dependent on each other with respect to their mutual interests. Both are under constant threats of the aggressive behaviour of China in the "Indo-Pacific region". Hence, for their mutual security, two nations have come closer under the umbrella of the Quad. The Quad has been playing a significant role to counter China's phenomenal rise. Most recently, in 2024 Quad Leaders' Summit held at Wilmington, Delaware, the United States, it was found that all the Quad partners (India, the US, Japan and Australia) were more aligned than ever before in the 21st Century, seeking the "Indo-Pacific region" "where no state dominates and no state is dominated". Above all, the close Indo-Japanese relations is not only important for two nations but also for the entire "Indo-Pacific region".

REFERENCES

- Alam, M.R. (2019). *The Indo-Japan Relationship: An Overview of the Current Scenario*. *World Affairs: The Journal of International Issues*, 23 (3), 102-107.
- Basu, T. (2014). *India-Japan Relations: An Enduring Partnership*. *Indian Foreign Affairs Journal*, 9 (3), 266-279.
- Kumar, P. (2020). *India-Japan Relations Under Modi 1.0: Exploring Political, Economic and Security Cooperation*. *World Affairs: The Journal of International Issues*, 24 (3), 42-53.
- Mohapatra, A. K. (2024). *Indo-Japan Relations: From Buddhism to Nuclear Cooperation*, *World Focus*, 45 (3), 18-21.
- Singh, M. (2022). *India Japan strategic relations and China factor post 2005*. *Shodhganga*. Retrieved November 23, 2024 from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/472740>
- Sahu, A. (2024). *India-Japan Relations @ 70: From Civilizational to Strategic Partnership*. *IJFMR*, 6 (4), 1-13.
- Sahoo, P. (2024). *India-China Border Dispute: Recent Clashes and their Consequences on Bilateral Relations*. *World Focus*, 45 (10), 52-56.
- Ladakh deadlock ends: India, China agrees on LAC Patrolling*. Retrieved November 24, 2024 from <https://timesofindia.indiatime.com>
- India-Japan Bilateral Relations*. Retrieved November 25, 2024 from <https://www.mea.gov.in>

Troops disengagement completed at Depsang and Demchok in eastern Ladakh. Retrieved December 7, 2024 from <https://www.thehindu.com>

Which Countries Border Japan? Retrieved December 7, 2024 from <https://www.worldatlas.com>

Japan. Retrieved December 9, 2024 from <https://www.britannica.com>

ASEAN-India Summit: PM Modi Meets Japanese Counterpart Ishiba , Leaders Reaffirm Commitment to Peaceful Indo-Pacific . Retrieved December 10, 2024 from <https://ddnews.gov.in>

Prime Minister meets with the Prime Minister of Japan on the sidelines of the ASEAN-India Summit. Retrieved December 11, 2024 from <https://www.mea.gov.in>

Prime Minister's meeting with the Prime Minister of Japan. Retrieved December 12, 2024 from <https://www.mea.gov.in>

India-Japan Relations. (Basic Data). Retrieved December 12, 2024 from <https://www.mofa.go.jp>

PM holds bilateral with Japanese counterpart Kishida on the sidelines of Quad Summit. Retrieved December 13, 2024 from <https://www.aninews.in>

Quad Summit: PM Modi Meets Japanese PM Fumio Kishida; Discusses Ways to Deepen Bilateral Ties. Retrieved December 14, 2024 from <https://ddnews.gov.in>